

Glycotwinning
Building Networks to
Excel in Glycoscience

Emerging technologies towards understanding the human glycome

Scientific Networking Meeting

03rd September '24

International leaders in
glycoscience will address the
current challenges and
opportunities in the field,
exploring the integration of
emerging technologies.

Welcome Letter

Dear Participants of the Scientific Network Meeting,

Glycoscience is a multidisciplinary research area focusing on the role of glycans in health and disease. The field is expanding rapidly worldwide, driving innovation in biomedical sciences and becoming an essential part of modern science, including medicine, and providing bases for understanding human diseases and tools for personalized medicine. GLYCOTwinning is a capacity-building network with the ambitious goal to promote scientific excellence and innovation in Glycoscience, empowering researchers' capacity and creativity through a strong synergy with top-class partners: IMPERIAL, LUMC and CIC bioGUNE.

We are delighted to have you join us for GLYCOTwinning Scientific Network Meeting, an exciting and intellectually stimulating event, that brings leading international experts in Glycoscience to explore and advance our understanding of the human glycome. Over the meeting, you will have the opportunity to listen the latest research and state-of-the-art developments in this rapidly evolving field, with a special focus on its far-reaching impacts on human health.

Our distinguished speakers will show us the current landscape of Glycoscience, highlighting groundbreaking discoveries and discussing future directions. This is also an invaluable opportunity for you to present your own research, engage in insightful discussions, and connect with peers and mentors who share your passion for this field.

We encourage you to take full advantage of the networking opportunities, which are integral to fostering collaborations that can lead to innovative solutions and new directions in Glycoscience.

Welcome to what promises to be a dynamic and enriching experience. We expect to make this meeting a milestone in your professional journey and in the advancement of Glycoscience!

Angelina S. Palma, Filipa Marcelo and Paula Videira

Acknowledgments

The organizing committee gratefully acknowledges the following organizations, which have contributed to its organization:

Project Coordinator

Consortium partners

Funding agencies

Scientific Committee

Angelina S. Palma | UCIBIO, FCT-NOVA

Filipa Marcelo | UCIBIO, FCT-NOVA

Paula A. Videira | UCIBIO, FCT-NOVA

Yan Liu | ICL

Manfred Wuhrer | LUMC

Organizing Committee (UCIBIO, FCT-NOVA)

Angelina S. Palma

Filipa Marcelo

Paula A. Videira

Ana Benavente

Benedita Pinheiro

Carlos Rodrigues

Filipa Trovão

Helena Coelho

Inês Teodoro

Mariana Barbosa

Tomé Azevedo

Zelia Silva

General Information

The Scientific Network Meeting will be held in the Library Auditorium (Floor -1) at the NOVA-FCT – in NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Portugal.

Registration, Lunch and Poster sessions will occur in Ágora Room, next to the campus' Library. Coffee break will be held near the Library Auditorium.

Parking

Free parking is available at the meeting venue, inside the faculty.

Speakers

Presenters are asked to upload their talks prior to their sessions by visiting the technician in the corresponding session room.

Poster Information

The posters should be displayed during the registration and kept throughout the day. Posters will be presented during the lunch time in Ágora Room.

Videoconference

To have online access to the open talks, the following Zoom link should be used:
<https://videoconf-colibri.zoom.us/j/6615379303>

Map of the event

Content

Scientific Programme	8
Invited Communications	9
Lectins as Tools for Deciphering and Targeting the Human Glycome	10
Exploring the Functions of Glycomes with Glycan Microarrays.....	11
Unveiling Siglec Interactions: Insights into Glycan and Antibody Binding Mechanisms	12
Uncovering the bacterial protein toolbox targeting the human glycome	14
Aberrant sialylation in colorectal cancer and novel platform for Glycomic Data Visualization .	15
Decoding the Molecular Basis of the Specificity of an anti-sTn Antibody.....	17
Application of biocatalysis in carbohydrate chemistry	18
Submitted Abstracts	19
Exploring glycan binding by <i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i> Fap2 adhesin for applications in cancer research.....	20
New Structural Insights of the <i>O</i> -Glycosylation Mechanism by C1GalT1 and ST6GalNAc-I....	21
CBMcarb-DB, a novel curated database at the interface of the structural and functional knowledge on CBMs and their carbohydrate ligands.....	22
Exploring the crosstalk between Sialyl-Tn (sTn) expression and the progression of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC).....	24
Insights into a Novel CBM from <i>Bacteroides Caccae</i> Targeting Tumour-Associated Mucin <i>O</i> -Glycan	26
Targeting Lectin-Mediated Immunosuppression with Tumour- Associated MUC1 <i>O</i> -Glycodomains: Synthesis and Lectin Recognition.....	27
Creating MGL-drug conjugates to specifically target cancer cells	29
Sialyl-Tn in Colorectal Cancer.....	31
Mucin glycoprotein microarray for glycan ligand discovery of bacterial modular proteins	32
It takes two to tango, the importance of microbial glycans in infectious diseases development.	34
Harnessing large-scale and single-cell RNA-Seq to Unveil the Landscape of Myeloid Lectins in Immunosuppressive Breast Cancer	36
Strategic Deciphering of Salmonella SiiE Adhesin Specificity for Advanced Anti-Adhesion Therapy.....	37
Glycosyltransferase 8 domain-containing protein 1 (GLT8D1) is a UDP-dependent galactosyltransferase	38
From Ratio to Reality: Compositional Analysis of Comparative Glycomics with Glycowork ...	39
GlyCoDA: A compositional data analysis and domain adaptation perspective on disease risk prediction using plasma IgG N-glycans	40
Targeting Human Macrophage Galactose-Type Lectin with Multivalent Glycomimetics	41

Advancing Understanding of Gut Microbiota-Glycosylation Interactions in Gastrointestinal Diseases: A Data-Driven Approach	42
Optimization of Cell Surface N-Glycoproteomics Analysis to Map the Colorectal Cancer Glycome	44
Streamlining oligosaccharide and glycan synthesis with mutant glycoside hydrolases.....	45
Direct imaging of single RNAs	46
Investigating Glycan Binding and Mutation Effects on SARS-CoV-2 N- Terminal Domain of spike protein on Viral Entry and Cell-Cell Fusion	47
Unveiling GlycoBiases: Biosynthetic network-driven insights into physiological glycan preferences of glycosyltransferases	48
Novel insights into mucin O-glycans recognition by commensal bacteria from the human gut microbiome.....	49

Scientific Programme

Tue 3/9 NOVA FCT Library Auditorium	
08:30 – 09:00	Registration
09:00 – 09:10	Opening Session GLYCOTwinning Coordinators NOVA FCT's Vice Dean for the Scientific Affairs - José Paulo Santos <i>Session 1 - Moderators: Zélia Silva and Ana Luísa Carvalho</i>
09:10 – 09:40	Lectins as tools for deciphering and targeting the human glycime – Anne Imberty
09:40 – 09:55	Cellular glycomics by mass spectrometry – Noortje de Haan
09:55 – 10:10	Exploring cellular glycomes by glycan microarrays – Yan Liu
10:10 – 10:25	Unveiling siglec interactions: insights into glycan and antibody binding mechanisms – June Ereño Orbea
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break <i>Session 2 - Moderators: Benedita Pinheiro and Helena Coelho</i>
11:00 – 11:15	Uncovering the bacterial protein toolbox targeting the human glycome – Angelina Sá Palma
11:15 – 11:30	Decoding the Molecular Basis of the Specificity of an anti-sTn Antibody - Filipa Marcelo
11:30 – 11:45	Aberrant sialylation in colorectal cancer and novel platform for Glycomic Data Visualization - Paula Videira
11:45 – 12:40	Flash presentations 1-7 (Round 1) and Q&A
12:40 – 14:30	Lunch & Poster Session (Ágora Room) UCIBIO Research unit director - Cecília Roque <i>Session 3 - Moderators: Filipa Trovão and Margarida Castro Caldas</i>
14:30 – 15:00	Hyphenated IM-MS methods for carbohydrate sequencing: a fragment-based approach – Sabine Flitsch
15:00 – 15:40	Flash presentations 8-13 (Round 2) and Q&A
14:40 – 15:50	GlycoNET - Elizabeth Nanak
15:50 – 16:50	Round Table Discussion: <i>The impact of Glycoscience across different disciplines</i> Panel GLYCOTwinning partners & invited speakers (Yan Liu, Jesús Jimenez-Barbero, Manfred Wuhrer, Anne Imberty, Sabine Flitsch, Serge Perez, António Jacinto) Moderator: Filipa Marcelo
16:50 – 17:00	Close up

Invited Communications

Lectins as Tools for Deciphering and Targeting the Human Glycome

Anne Imberty

Université Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, CERMAV, 38000 Grenoble, France

anne.imberty@cermav.cnrs.fr

A large number of pathogenic microorganisms display receptors for specific recognition and adhesion to the glycoconjugates present on human tissues. In addition to membrane-bound adhesins, soluble lectins are involved in lung infections caused by the bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Burkholderia cepacia* and by the fungus *Aspergillus fumigatus* that are responsible for hospital-acquired diseases. The multivalency of lectin is proposed to play a role in their strong avidity for glycosylated cell surfaces, their specific binding to some cell types, and also in their ability to affect membrane dynamics by clustering glycosphingolipids, resulting in some cases in internalization of intracellular pathogens.

Accumulated knowledge about the structures of the lectins and the interactions with host glycoconjugates has led to the design of powerful glyco-derived inhibitors that can serve as antimicrobial therapeutic agents, as a complement to or an alternative to antibiotic therapy. Several strategies are developed: glycoderivatives with increased affinity, glycomimetics with no carbohydrate moiety or multivalent compounds that make use of the receptor architecture. On the other hand, bacterial lectins are superb tools for identifying, purifying and labelling glycoconjugates and can be used for vectorisation or as glue for creating artificial tissue. Synthetic glycobiology offers innovative methods for building super-lectins as novel architectures.

Exploring the Functions of Glycomes with Glycan Microarrays

Yan Liu

*Glycosciences Laboratory, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction,
Faculty of Medicine, Imperial College London, London, W12 0NN, United Kingdom*

yan.liu2@imperial.ac.uk

The interactions of glycans with their binding partners, governed by an intricate 'glyco-code', influence many of the key biological processes in all living organisms. As prominent host cell surface molecules, glycans mediate cell adhesion and trigger cell signalling, and serve as attachment sites for microbes playing a critical role in colonization and infection. Glycan microarray technologies, first introduced in 2002 by Professor Ten Feizi and colleagues at Imperial College London (ICL), have revolutionized approaches to the molecular dissection of glycan-protein interactions and gained significant momentum worldwide. The ICL Carbohydrate Microarray Facility, since its foundation in 2012, has become an internationally leading operation, enabling collaborative studies on diverse glycan-mediated interactions involving the broad biomedical community (<https://www.imperial.ac.uk/glycosciences/carbohydrate-microarray-facility/>). I will highlight the unique resource we possess within our Facility, our recent contributions to unraveling glycan-mediated interactions at the host-microbe interface, and the latest advances in generating glycome-scale microarrays.

Acknowledgments

Our work has been supported by the Wellcome Trust Biomedical Resource Grants (WT099197/Z/12/Z, 108430/Z/15/Z and 218304/Z/19/Z), ICL-March of Dimes European Prematurity Research Center grant (22-FY18-82), MRC Research Grant (MR/R010757/1), and the Horizon Europe guarantee scheme (administered by UKRI) for the EU Horizon-CSA grant for the "GLYCOTwinning" project (101079417).

Unveiling Siglec Interactions: Insights into Glycan and Antibody Binding Mechanisms

Klaudia Sobczak, Iker Oyenarte, Unai Atxabal, Andrea Fernández, Pablo Valverde, Eunat Valdalisó, M Pia Lenza, M Elena Laugieri, Leire Egia-Mendikute, Asier Antoñana, Alexandre Bosch, Asis Palazón, and Jesús Jiménez-Barbero, June Ereño-Orbea

Cancer Glycoimmunology & Chemical Glycobiology labs, CIC bioGUNE, Bizkaia Technology Park, 48160, Derio (Spain)
IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science and Technology, Euskadi Plaza 5, 48009, Bilbao (Spain)
jereno@cicbiogune.es

Hypersialylation, an aberrant increase in the expression of sialic acid, profoundly impacts tumor cell interactions with their microenvironment. Siglecs, immune receptors that recognize cell surface sialic acids, play a pivotal role in immune surveillance within the tumor microenvironment. Our group has studied the interaction between glycans containing sialic acids (sialoglycans) and Siglec receptors on immune cells, demonstrating that this pathway can be targeted to regulate immune responses and control tumor growth. Leveraging structural biology techniques, including X-ray crystallography, NMR, and molecular dynamics, we have scrutinized the molecular details governing their specificities for sialoglycans¹⁻⁶. This information offers opportunities for developing novel molecules targeting Siglecs through modified sialic acids. Our research also focuses on uncovering structural insights on anti-Siglec antibodies to refine antibody-based therapies.

References

1. J. Ereño-Orbea, T. Sicard, T. H. Cui, M.T. Mazhab-Jafari, S. Benlekbir, A. Guarné, J. Rubinstein, J.P. Julien. Molecular Basis of Human CD22 Function and Therapeutic Targeting. *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, 8 (764), 764.
2. J. Ereño-Orbea, X. Liu, T. Sicard, I. Kucharska, W. Li, D. Borovsky, H. Cui, Y. Feng, D.S. Dimitrov, J.P. Julien. Structural Details of Monoclonal Antibody M971 Recognition of the Membrane Proximal Domain of CD22. *J. Biol. Chem.* **2021**, 297 (2), 100966.
3. M.P. Lenza, U. Atxabal, C. Nycholat, I. Oyenarte, A. Franconetti, J.I. Quintana, S. Delgado, R. Núñez-Franco, C.T. Garnica Marroquín, H. Coelho, et al, J. Jiménez-Barbero, J. Ereño-Orbea. Structures of the Inhibitory Receptor Siglec-8 in Complex with a High-Affinity Sialoside Analogue and a Therapeutic Antibody. *JACS Au.* **2022**, 3 (1), 204-215.
4. M.P. Lenza, L. Egia-Mendikute, A. Antoñana-Vildosola, C.O. Soares, H. Coelho, F. Corzana, A. Bosch, P. Manisha, J.I. Quintana, I. Oyenarte, et al, J. Jiménez-Barbero, A. Palazon, J. Ereño-Orbea. Structural Insights into Siglec-15 Reveal Glycosylation Dependency for Its Interaction with T Cells through Integrin CD11b. *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, 14 (1), 3496.
5. U. Atxabal, C. Nycholat, J. Pröpster, et al, J. C. Paulson, J. Jiménez-Barbero, J. Ereño-Orbea. Unraveling molecular recognition of glycan ligands by Siglec-9 via NMR spectroscopy and molecular dynamics modelling. *ACS Chem. Biol.* **2024**, 19 (2), 483-496.
6. U. Atxabal, A. Fernández, M. Moure, K. Sobczak, et al., J. Jiménez-Barbero, J. Ereño-Orbea. Quantifying Siglec-Sialylated Ligand Interactions: A versatile 19F-T2 CPMG-Filtered Competitive NMR Displacement Assay. *Chem. Sci.* **2024**, 15 (27), 10612-10624.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from AEI & MICIU (Spain), EU-GlycoTwinning, EU-Glytunes, and BBVA Leonardo.

Uncovering the bacterial protein toolbox targeting the human glycome

Angelina S. Palma^{1,2}

1. UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

2. Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

angelina.palma@fct.unl.pt

Glycans are essential players in bacterial-host interactions comprising recognition sites for both commensal and pathogenic bacteria, contributing to shaping the resident bacterial population at the gut epithelial mucosal surface. Emerging research is uncovering gut bacterial mechanisms that use host glycans as nutrients or degrade them during pathogen invasion. A paradigm in human microbiome research relates to the ability of some commensal bacteria, such as *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* and *B. caccae*, to forage on mucin O-glycans from the mucus protecting layer of the gut epithelia, using these as nutrients or attachment sites, enhancing their competitiveness to colonise, particularly in a low fibre diet. Commensal bacteria that can recognize host-glycans influence not only the host response but also colonic health, promoting states of dysbiosis and susceptibility to infection.

How mucin O-glycans are differentially exploited by human microbiome bacteria and influence the crosstalk with the host largely remains to be elucidated at the molecular level. In this communication, I will overview the characterization of newly identified glycan-binding proteins from these bacteria, which are encoded by sets of co-regulated genes termed *polysaccharide utilization loci* systems (PULs) targeting a specific glycan structure. Through sequence and structural bioinformatic analysis of the bacterial genomes, we selected putative glycan-binding proteins for high-throughput production and ligand discovery using glycan microarrays. Structural characterization of proteins targeting mucin O-GalNAc-Thr/Ser cores and Tn antigen by X-ray crystallography led to uncovering their molecular determinants for mucin O-glycan recognition. These and their associated putative O-glycan selective catalytic domains are being investigated for their biotechnological exploitation as a molecular protein toolbox to target human glycans. We anticipate this study to help understand the role of commensal bacteria in gut health and in designing new therapeutic and diagnostic strategies.

Acknowledgments

This work has been supported by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology for grants PTDC/BIA-MIB/31730/2017 and 2022.06104.PTDC; the Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit - UCIBIO (UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020) and the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB (LA/P/0140/2020) and by the European Commission through HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning project.

Aberrant sialylation in colorectal cancer and novel platform for Glycomic Data Visualization

Rita Adubeiro Lourenço^{1,2}, Daniela Pinto^{1,2}, Daniela Barreira^{1,2,3}, Marta Martins⁴, Raquel Cruz Duarte⁴, Sandra Casimiro⁴, Paula Borralho⁴, Luís Costa^{4,5}, Oleg Mayboroda⁶, Noortje De Haan⁶, Manfred Wuhrer⁶, Ana Rita Grosso^{1,2}, Paula Videira^{1,2,3}

¹ *i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Largo da Torre, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

² *Departamento Ciências da Vida, UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

³ *CDG & Allies – Professionals and Patient Associations International Network (CDG & Allies – PPAIN), 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

⁴ *Instituto de Medicina Molecular-João Lobo Antunes, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal.*

⁵ *Oncology Division, Hospital de Santa Maria, Centro Hospitalar Lisboa Norte, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal.*

⁶ *Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics, Leiden University Medical Center, Netherlands.*

p.videira@fct.unl.pt

Aberrant sialylation patterns, characterized by the elevated presence of atypical sialylated glycans such as the cancer-associated antigen sialyl-Tn (STn), are commonly observed in cancer cells. STn's occurrence on cell surface glycoproteins generally correlates with poor prognosis and an immunosuppressive microenvironment, highlighting its potential as a diagnostic biomarker and therapeutic target in cancer research and treatment. This study explores the clinical and biological relevance of STn in triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) and colorectal cancer (CRC). By applying immunohistochemistry to tumour tissue samples from patients, we aim to correlate STn expression with clinical outcomes and gain deeper insights into the role of this truncated O-glycan. Using transcriptomic data from CRC tumour tissues and immunohistochemistry staining for the STn, we were able to establish a correlation between STn expression and the *ST6GALNAC1* gene, alongside other genes important for glycosylation processes. Additionally, exploiting the cancer transcriptome available from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) for both CRC and TNBC, we employed the *ST6GALNAC1* gene expression to explore this biomarker at the gene level. Our findings revealed reduced overall survival associated with STn expression in the TNBC tissue cohort and increased cell proliferation in the TNBC MDA-MB-231 cell line overexpressing the STn antigen. Moreover, we identified a significant negative correlation with c-Myc, potentially explained by the significant positive correlation with genes involved in the TGF- β pathway. Additionally, a substantial proportion of gene signatures associated *ST6GALNAC1* gene expression with immune regulation genes. Subsequent analysis unveiled a positive correlation between *ST6GALNAC1* expression and the presence of immune cell infiltrates, particularly macrophage M2 and regulatory T

cells, suggesting potential immunosuppressive regulatory mechanisms shaping the tumour microenvironment. These analyses provide comprehensive insights into the impact of *ST6GALNAC1* expression on biological processes and immune cell infiltration, thereby enhancing our understanding of cancer pathology. Additionally, the use of cell lines expressing STn or other pertinent O-glycans presents an opportunity for in vitro validation of our findings. In support of this, a platform for the interactive visualization of cancer cell line glycomes is currently being developed through the GLYCOTwinning project.

References

1. Carrascal MA, Severino PF, Guadalupe Cabral M, Silva M, Ferreira JA, Calais F, Quinto H, Pen C, Ligeiro D, Santos LL, Dall'Olio F, Videira PA. Sialyl Tn-expressing bladder cancer cells induce a tolerogenic phenotype in innate and adaptive immune cells. *Mol Oncol*. 2014 May;8(3):753-65. doi: 10.1016/j.molonc.2014.02.008. Epub 2014 Mar 6. PMID: 24656965; PMCID: PMC5528624.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) as fellowships SFRH/BD/148480/2019 (RAL) and 2020.09880.BD (DB), as project InnoGlyco (ref: 2022.04607.PTDC) and under grants UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (provided to the Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit – UCIBIO), LA/P/0140/2020 (provided to the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy – i4HB). This work was also supported by the European Commission through the GLYCOTwinning project (Grant Agreement: 101079417).

Decoding the Molecular Basis of the Specificity of an anti-sTn Antibody

Cátia O. Soares,^{1,2} María Elena Laugieri,³ Mariangela Natale,^{1,2} Ana Sofia Grosso,^{1,2} Helena Coelho,^{1,2} Ulrika Westerlind,⁴ Jesús Jiménez-Barbero,³ Angelina S. Palma,^{1,2} Paula A. Videira,^{1,2} June Ereño-Orbea,³ Filipa Marcelo^{1,2}

1. UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; 2. Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; 3. CIC bioGUNE, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Bizkaia Technology Park, Ed. 800. E-48160, Derio, Spain; 4. Department of Chemistry, Umeå University, 901 87 Umeå, Sweden

filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

sTn-antigen is a promising target for therapeutic and diagnostic applications, and for that purpose research efforts have been devoted to developing anti-sTn antibodies.^{1,2,3} However, the enhancement of the specificity of anti-sTn antibodies is of paramount importance for their use as tumour immunotherapeutic or/and diagnostic applications. In this context, for the elucidation of anti-sTn antibodies' specificity and for a rational improvement of their recognition towards cancer cells is essential to establish a robust structure-driven approach to decipher the molecular basis of anti-sTn antibodies' recognition. Through an integrative and multidisciplinary approach, the molecular determinants, behind the anti- α 2,6-sialic acid L2A5 antibody's specificity, were exhaustively scrutinized, and will be described in this presentation.

References

1. D. M. 1. L. R. Loureiro et al. Sci Rep. 2018, 8, 1–16.
2. J. M. Prendergast, et al. MAbs 2017, 9, 615–627.
3. Database of Anti-Glycan Reagents (DAGR; <https://ccr2.cancer.gov/resources/Cbl/Tools/Antibody/>)

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning funded by European Commission. The authors also thank to Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) for the funding projects: UCIBIO project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 and Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB project LA/P/0140/2020). F.M. and H.C. thanks FCT-Portugal for the CEEC contract CEECINST/00042/2021 and 2020.03261.CEECIND, respectively. C. O. S. acknowledges the PhD grant 2022.11723.BD. The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013- PINFRA/22161/2016, cofinanced by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC).

Application of biocatalysis in carbohydrate chemistry

Sabine L Flitsch

MIB, The University of Manchester, 131 Princess Street M1 7DN, UK

Sabine.Flitsch@manchester.ac.uk

Carbohydrate active enzymes provide useful tools for the analysis and synthesis of glycans, and the toolbox of these biocatalysts is expanding in terms of reaction diversity and substrate range. Whilst enzymes have been used widely for native biochemical reactions, it is now increasingly possible to design and engineer biocatalysts that can also be used for non-natural reactions with much wider substrate scope^{1,2}. This lecture will discuss a variety of applications of biocatalysts to the synthesis of modified carbohydrates such as protected sugar building blocks³, deoxy-fluoro sugars^{4,5}, imino sugars^{6,7} and glycoconjugates such as glycoproteins^{8,9} and antibodies^{10,11}.

References

1. E.L. Bell et al. (2021) *Nature Reviews Methods Primer* (1) 46.
2. W. Finnigan et al. (2021) *Nature Catalysis* (4) 98.
3. A. Marchesi et al. (2020) *Angew. Chem.* (59) 22456.
4. P. Valverde et al. (2020) *Chem. Commun.* (56) 6408.
5. K. Hollingsworth, A. Di Maio et al. (2024) *Nature Communications*. (In Press)
6. G. Ford et al. (2022) *JACS AU* (2) 2251.
7. C.R.B. Swanson et al. (2023) *ACS Central Science* (9) 103.
8. E.G. Pallister et al. (2020) *Biochemistry* (59) 3123.
9. A. Matthey et al. (2019) *ACS Catalysis* (9) 8208.
10. A. Angelastro et al. (2022) *ChemSusChem* (15) e202102592.
11. A. Angelastro et al. (2024) *Nature Synthesis* (3) 976–985.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from the European Research Council (788231- ProgrES-ERC-2017-ADG) and RCUK

Submitted Abstracts

*Underlined are the abstracts selected for Flash presentations

Exploring glycan binding by *Fusobacterium nucleatum* Fap2 adhesin for applications in cancer research

**Ana Luísa Benavente¹, Filipa Trovão^{1,2}, Carlos Rodrigues¹, Angelina S. Palma^{1,2},
Benedita Pinheiro^{1,2}**

1. UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

2. Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal

a.benavente@campus.fct.unl.pt

Mucin-type O-glycosylation of cell-surface and secreted proteins is associated with cell development and differentiation. Alterations of O-glycosylation also modulate aggressive colorectal cancer (CRC) phenotypes, and tumor associated O-glycans are crucial molecular targets for therapy and as clinical biomarkers. Research on the human microbiome uncovered that dysbiosis with an unbalanced abundance of *Fusobacterium nucleatum* leads to a pro-inflammatory milieu, promoting tumor growth¹. Evidence shows the role of recognition of tumor-expressed glycans by the *F. nucleatum* adhesin Fap2 in mediating signalling in CRC. Still, it is unknown how CRC-associated glycans are differentially recognised by Fap2 adhesin. In this communication, we will present initial results aiming at the characterization of Fap2 glycan-binding specificity, combining protein structural analysis and human O-glycome microarrays. Ultimately, the goal is to elucidate how O-glycans are exploited by bacteria at a molecular level and identify protein targets to modulate bacterial adhesion to cancer cell models. Through bioinformatic sequence and structural analysis of Fap2 adhesin, several Fap2 fragments spanning the entire Fap2 extracellular domain were designed and expressed as recombinant proteins. Initial data showed structured and functional Fap2 fragments with interaction to terminal galactosylated glycoproteins, and sialylation inhibiting the binding.

References

1. M. A. McGuckin, S. K. Lindén, P. Sutton, and T. H. Florin, *Nature Reviews Microbiology* 2011, 9, 265–278; 2. Abed et al., *Cell Host & Microbe*, 2016, 20, 215–225.

Acknowledgments

Financial support from the Portuguese Science and Technology Foundation GlycOSELECT 2022.06104.PTDC and European funds (HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning); The Research Unit on Applied Molecular Biosciences – UCIBIO (UIDP/04378/2020, UIDB/04378/2020) and the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB (LA/P/0140/2020). We thank Dr. Daniel Roderer and Felix Schöpf (FMP Berlin) for the collaboration to obtain the full length Fap2 adhesin, as well as N-terminal Fap2 constructs and other adhesins of interest in the context of the project.

New Structural Insights of the O-Glycosylation Mechanism by C1GalT1 and ST6GalNAc-I

A. S. Grosso,^{1,2} A. González-Ramírez,³ J. Gomes,⁴ H. Coelho,^{1,2} F. García-Martín⁵, C. A. Reis,⁴ R. Hurtado-Guerrero,³ F. Corzana,⁵ F. Marcelo^{1,2}

¹UCIBIO, REQUIMTE, Departamento de Química, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Caparica, Portugal, ²I4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Caparica, Portugal, ³BIFI-IQFR (CSIC), Universidad de Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain, ⁴i3S/Upatimup, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal, ⁵Department of Chemistry, Universidad de La Rioja, Logroño, Spain

a.grosso@campus.fct.unl.pt; filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

Mucin-type O-glycosylation is a complex mechanism regulated by the coordinated activity of specific glycosyltransferases (GTs)¹. Altered regulation of several GTs is a common feature of cancer that results in tumour-associated carbohydrate antigens (TACAs)¹. Two of the most popular TACAs are the TF- (Gal β 1-3GalNAc α 1-O-Ser/Thr) and sTn (Neu5Ac α 2-6GalNAc α 1-O-Ser/Thr) antigens. The TF-antigen is formed exclusively by C1GalT1, which transfers a Gal residue from the sugar donor UDP-Gal to GalNAc-containing peptides². This antigen naturally present as a hidden part of more complex O-glycans, in cancer cells appears exposed¹. The sTn antigen, exclusively found in cancer cells, is generated by ST6GalNAc-I, which adds a Neu5Ac residue from the CMP-Neu5Ac sugar donor to GalNAc-containing peptides³. Despite the importance of C1GalT1 and ST6GalNAc-I in health and disease, their molecular mechanism remains elusive. Therefore, understanding the molecular basis behind C1GalT1 and ST6GalNAc-I molecular mechanism of catalysis and recognition towards the Tn-antigen is of extreme importance to develop targeting strategies towards both enzymes.

Herein, new structural and conformational insights will be highlighted with a multidisciplinary approach mainly focused on NMR spectroscopy and molecular dynamic simulations.

References

- 12.S. S. Pinho, C. A. Reis, Nat. Ver. Cancer, 2015, 15, 540-555.
- 13.M. González-Ramírez, A. S. Grosso, Z. Yang, I. Compañón, H. Coelho, Y. Narimatsu, H. Clausen,
- 14.F. Marcelo, F. Corzana, R. Hurtado-Guerrero, Nat. Commun., 2022, 13, 1-15.
- 15.N. T. Marcos, S. Pinho, C. Grandela, A. Cruz, B. Samyn-Petit, A. Harduin-Lepers, R. Almeida, F. Silva, V. Morais, J. Costa, J. Kihlberg, H. Clausen, C. A. Reis, Cancer Research, 2004, 64, 7050-7057.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from FCT-Portugal: IF/00780/2015; PTDC/BIA-MIB/31028/2017; PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020; UCIBIO UIDB/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020; Infrastructure project 22161; LA/P/0140/2020, PhD grants SFRH/BD/140394/2018 and COVID/BD/152986/2023.

CBMcarb-DB, a novel curated database at the interface of the structural and functional knowledge on CBMs and their carbohydrate ligands

**Ana Luísa Carvalho^{1,2}, Diana O. Ribeiro^{1,2}, François Bonnardel³, Luís Gomes⁴,
Angelina S. Palma^{1,2}, Serge Perez³**

1. UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

2. Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal

3. Centre de Recherche sur les Macromolécules Végétales, University Joseph Fourier in Grenoble, France

4. Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade de Lisboa, Portugal

almc@fct.unl.pt

Carbohydrate Binding Modules (CBMs) are a structural and functional diverse class of carbohydrate-binding proteins, classified and annotated in the CAZY database into different families based on amino acid sequence similarity [1]. CBMs are typically found as ancillary non-catalytic protein domains of modular enzymes, enhancing catalytic efficiency, but can also function isolated or associated with other non-enzymatic proteins. The number of newly identified putative CBM sequences is growing fast due to the exponential increase of sequence information derived from genomics, metagenomics and transcriptomics data, particularly for microbial organisms. CBMs show diverse carbohydrate-binding specificities between families and even within the same family. Several characterized CBMs are associated with bacterial and fungal systems that recognize non-crystalline cellulose and chitin, insoluble storage polysaccharides, and different hemicellulosic substrates[1,3]. Recently, attention has been drawn to CBMs from bacterial pathogens and commensal bacteria, which can recognize the complex glycosylation of mucins [2]. CBMs interact with carbohydrates through various non-covalent interactions, such as hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic interactions, CH- π interactions, van der Waals forces, and electrostatic interactions. The ligand binding site of CBMs is usually composed of aromatic residues that form a flat, groove, or pocket-shaped surface that matches the shape and size of the ligand. However, other molecular determinants are involved in making a CBM-carbohydrate complex, and the network of interactions confer specificity for a given carbohydrate. Hence, CBMs are an excellent model for studying protein-carbohydrate interactions. Here, we will describe the development and application of CBMcarb-DB, a novel database dedicated to displaying and analyzing the 3D structures of CBM-carbohydrate complexes[4,5,6]. CBMcarb-DB provides curated structural data about CBM-carbohydrate binding interactions, carbohydrate conformation, and functional information on binding specificity. CBMcarb-DB contributes to establishing an integrated web-based platform that combines structural and functional knowledge of CBMs and their carbohydrate ligands, important for

exploiting CBMs for various biotechnological applications, including generating engineered CBMs with diverse new functional properties[3].

References

1. E. Drula, M.-L. Garron, S. Dogan, V. Lombard, B. Henrissat and N. Terrapon, *Nucleic Acids Res*, 2022, 50, D571–D577
2. S. Etzold and N. Juge, *Curr Opin Struct Biol*, 2014, 28, 23–31.
3. D.O. Ribeiro, B.A. Pinheiro, A.L. Carvalho and A.S. Palma, *Carbohydrate Chemistry: Chemical and Biological Approaches Vol. 43*. The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2018. 159-176.
4. D.O. Ribeiro, F. Bonnardel, A.S. Palma, A.L.M. Carvalho and S. Perez, *Carbohydrate Chemistry: Chemical and Biological Approaches Vol. 46*. The Royal Society of Chemistry, 2024. 1-22

Acknowledgments

Funding by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology for grants PTDC/BIA-MIB/31730/2017 and 2022.06104.PTDC; the Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit - UCIBIO (UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020) and the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB (LA/P/0140/2020). We also acknowledge the project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning, financed by European funds, the COST Action Innogly CA18103 for Virtual Mobility Grant to DR (E-COST-GRANT-CA18103-02b37039), and the CrossDisciplinary Program Glyco@Alps within the framework 'Investissement d'Avenir' program [ANR- 15IDEX-02].

Exploring the crosstalk between Sialyl-Tn (STn) expression and the progression of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC)

Ana C. F. Soares^{1,2}, Mireia Castillo-Martin³, Rita Adubeiro Lourenço^{1,2}, Daniela Pinto^{1,2}, Paula A. Videira^{1,2}

¹ UCIBIO - Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Life Sciences, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Caparica, Portugal

² Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal.

³ Champalimaud Foundation, Lisbon, Portugal

acf.soares@campus.fct.unl.pt; p.videira@fct.unl.pt

Keywords: Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma; Sialyl-Tn; Immunohistochemistry

Introduction: Pancreatic cancer (PC) is expected to become the second-leading cause of cancer-related deaths in the next decade ⁽¹⁾. The most common and deadliest form of PC derives from the exocrine pancreas being designated pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) ⁽²⁾. Since an efficient target treatment does not exist, surgery is currently the most successful clinical treatment. Yet, these patients have a low long-term survival rate ⁽³⁾. Therefore, new therapeutic targets are needed to surpass this limitation. Sialyl-Tn (STn) is a carbohydrate antigen that results from incomplete synthesis of branched O-glycan chains, mostly due to overexpression of sialyltransferase ST6GalNAc1⁽⁴⁾. This short sialylated O-glycan is associated with poor prognosis and immunosuppressive microenvironment since it contributes to cancer progression and metastasis ^{(4),(5)}. While PDAC is known to over-express truncated O-glycans ⁽⁶⁾, the STn profiling and role in different PC stages is elusive. Herein, we aim to investigate STn's impact in PDAC progression, elucidating its role as a possible therapeutic target.

Materials and Methods: An immunohistochemistry assay was conducted to evaluate the STn expression in 186 human pancreatic cancer tissues in different stages. The cohort included treated and untreated PDAC surgery samples, metastases samples, and precursor lesions samples such as intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasm (IPMN) and pancreatic intraepithelial neoplasia (PanIN). STn expression quantification was made using the H-score, considering the apical and cytoplasmic staining intensity and excluding the expression in the mucus.

Results: In our cohort, the normal pancreas rarely expressed STn antigen. The majority of the stained PDAC cases without treatment stained positive for STn and presented high expression. The PDAC post-chemotherapy cases showed a slight decrease in STn expression and IPMN precursor lesions revealed high heterogeneity in the staining. The high-grade dysplasia PanIN precursor lesion presented higher STn expression intensity when compared to low-grade dysplasia PanINs. The metastasis in lung, diaphragm, and liver, also presented high STn expression, except for one case in the liver. Furthermore, PC as well as other cancer cells human cell lines overexpressing ST6GalNAc1 showed

prominent expression of STn suggesting the aberrant expression of this enzyme as causative of STn aberrant expression.

Discussion: These results highlight the tumour specificity of STn and suggests a role for STn in cancer progression. Our data will enable correlation of STn with clinical features, and gene expression that may be common to other cancer types. Furthermore, we aim to validate STn-related immunophenotype from this cohort and then proceed to an *in vivo* mouse model and finally test anti-STn antibodies' efficacy in overcoming immunosuppression and reducing tumour progression using an *in vitro* model.

Conclusion: STn expression shows tumour specificity in PC, increasing from pre-malignant to malignant types and increased in metastatic lesions, suggesting its potential role in disease progression.

References

16. Ansari D, Tingstedt B, Andersson B, Holmquist F, Stureson C, Williamsson C, et al. Pancreatic cancer: Yesterday, today and tomorrow. *Futur Oncol*. 2016;12(16):1929-46.
17. Mollinedo F, Gajate C. Novel therapeutic approaches for pancreatic cancer by combined targeting of RAF→MEK→ERK signaling and autophagy survival response. *Ann Transl Med*. 2019;7(S3):S153–S153.
18. Vincent A, Herman J, Schulick R, Hruban RH, Goggins M. Pancreatic cancer. *Lancet* [Internet]. 2011;378(9791):607–20. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)62307-0](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)62307-0)
19. Carrascal MA, Severino PF, Guadalupe Cabral M, Silva M, Ferreira JA, Calais F, et al. Sialyl Tn-expressing bladder cancer cells induce a tolerogenic phenotype in innate and adaptive immune cells. *Mol Oncol*. 2014;8(3):753–65.
20. Julien S, Videira PA, Delannoy P. Sialyl-Tn in cancer: (How) did we miss the target? *Biomolecules*. 2012;2(4):435–66.
21. Radhakrishnan P, Dabelsteen S, Madsen FB, Francavilla C, Kopp KL, Steentoft C, et al. Immature truncated O-glycophenotype of cancer directly induces oncogenic features. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 2014;111(39):E4066–75.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) Portugal, under grants SFRH/BD/148480/2019 provided to RAL and UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 (provided to the Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit – UCIBIO), LA/P/0140/2020 (provided to the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy – i4HB), by InnO-Glyco project (2022.04607.PTDC), by the European Commission through the GLYCOTwinning project (Grant Agreement: 101079417), and by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the EJPRD COFUND-EJP N 825575 (EJPRD/0001/2020).

Insights into a Novel CBM from *Bacteroides Caccae* Targeting Tumour-Associated Mucin O-Glycan

A. Candeias^{a,b}, F. Trovão^{a,b}, C.O. Soares^{a,b}, A.S. Grosso^{a,b}, F. Marcelo^{a,b}, B. A. Pinheiro^{a,b}, A.L. Carvalho^{a,b}, A. S. Palma^{a,b}

^aAssociate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal
^bUCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal
ai.candeias@fct.unl.pt

The gastrointestinal tract harbors a diverse community of commensal bacteria that impacts on human health. In a low-fiber diet, some commensal bacteria can switch to host mucin O-glycoproteins as alternative substrates. In this context, the commensal *Bacteroides caccae* was implicated in the deconstruction of the colonic mucous layer, increasing susceptibility to pathogen infection and progression of intestinal diseases^{1,2}. During growth of *B. caccae* on mucin O-glycans, an increase of the expression of modular enzymes, including modular M60-like metallopeptidases (also known as mucinases), with appended non-catalytic carbohydrate-binding modules of family 32 (CBM32), is observed². These enzymes are organized in gene clusters, termed polysaccharide utilization loci (PUL), which encode all the genes necessary for the breakdown and uptake of a given glycan³. Herein, we describe our research advancement using an integrative approach to uncover glycan recognition by a novel CBM32 (BC16100-CBM) appended to a putative mucinase of PUL-53. Analysis using a MUC-1 O-glycopeptide microarray, combined with affinity studies, showed a remarkable specificity towards GalNAc-Ser/GalNAc-Thr (Tn antigen). The molecular determinants of Tn-antigen recognition by BC16100-CBM were elucidated combining NMR and X-ray Crystallography. This data shows the first clues of the molecular mechanism behind the recognition of tumour-associated antigens and utilization of mucin substrates by *B. caccae*.

References

1. E. C. Martens, M. Neumann and M. S. Desai, Nat. Rev. Microbiol., 2018, 16, 457–470;
2. M. S. Desai et al, Cell, 2016, 167, 1339-1353;
3. P. Rahfeld, J. F. Wardman, K. Mehr, D. Huff, C. Morgan-Lang, H. M. Chen, S. J. Hallam and S. G. Withers, J. Biol. Chem., 2019, 294, 16400–16415D.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge funding from Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) through the grants 2022.06104.PTDC and RECI/BBB-BEP/0124/2012; the CEEC contract CEECINST/00042/2021 to F.M.; and the PhD grants SFRH/BD/143494/2019 and 2022.11723.BD to F.T. and C.O.S. The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013-PINFRA/22161/2016, cofinanced by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC). A.C., F.M. and A.P. acknowledge the GLYCOTwinning project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417 funded by European Commission.

Targeting Lectin-Mediated Immunosuppression with Tumour-Associated MUC1 O-Glycodomains: Synthesis and Lectin Recognition

Cátia O. Soares,^{1,2} Ana S. Grosso,^{1,2} Helena Coelho,^{1,2} Carlos D. L. Lima,^{1,2} Alejandra Travecedo,^{1,2} David Sánchez-Navarro,³ Irene Ginés Alcober,³ Ramón-Hurtado Guerrero,³ Jesús Jiménez-Barbero,^{5,6} June Ereño-Orbea,^{5,6} & Filipa Marcelo^{1,2}

1. UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; 2. Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; 3. Institute of Biocomputation and Physics of Complex Systems (BIFI), Glycobiology Unit, University of Zaragoza, Mariano Esquillor s/n, Campus Rio Ebro, Edificio I+D, 50018 Zaragoza, Spain. 5. CIC bioGUNE, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Bizkaia Technology Park, Ed. 800. E-48160, Derio, Spain; 6. Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, Euskadi Plaza 5, 48009 Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain

ca.soares@campus.fct.unl.pt; filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

Aberrant O-glycosylation of Mucin-1 (MUC1) is a hallmark feature in cancer.¹ In malignancy, MUC1 O-glycans become truncated, due to changes in the expression, location or activity of glycosyltransferases, resulting in new glycan epitopes recognized by lectins.¹ Through this binding event, lectins such as Siglecs, Galectins and MGL, trigger pro-tumour immunological responses and promote metastasis.² Therefore, strategies to disrupt these tumour-glycan/lectin interactions are essential to potentially alleviate anti-tumour immunosuppression and reduce metastasis.

Herein, short MUC1 O-glycodomains that mimic tumour-associated MUC1, were chemoenzymatically synthesized. The products carry different tumour-associated glycans, specifically the Tn antigen (GalNAc α 1O-Ser/Thr) and the sTn antigen (Neu5Ac α 2,6GalNAc α 1O-Ser/Thr), in distinct density schemes (two or five antigens in each of the four tandem repeats). The molecular recognition of these MUC1 O-glycodomains by the lectins Siglec-7 and MGL was investigated using high-resolution NMR, specifically through ¹H, ¹⁵N- and ¹H, ¹³C-HSQC titrations from the perspective of the ¹³C, ¹⁵N-labelled MUC1 O-glycodomains. These structural studies will enhance the understanding of how these types of multivalent ligands are recognized by these lectins, aiding in the selection of the best candidates for future immunological assays to evaluate their potential as immunomodulators.

References

1. D. M. Beckwith & M. Cudic, *Semin. Immunol.*, 2020, 47, 101389
2. E. Rodríguez, S. T. T. Schetters, & Y. Van Kooyk, *Nat. Rev. Immunol.*, 2018, 18, 204–211

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) for the funding projects: MGL4Life DOI 10.54499/PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020, UCIBIO projects UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 and i4HB project LA/P/0140/2020. C. O. S., C.L., and A.S.G. acknowledge the PhD grants 2022.11723.BD, 2021.06789.BD., and SFRH/BD/140394/2018 (including COVID/BD/152986/2023), respectively. H.C. and F.M. thank FCT-Portugal for the CEEC contracts 2020.03261.CEECIND and CEECINST/00042/2021, respectively. The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013- PINFRA/22161/2016, cofinanced by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC). F.M. and J.J.B. acknowledge the project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning financed by European funds.

Creating MGL-drug conjugates to specifically target cancer cells

Carlos D. L. Lima,^{1,2} **João P. M. António**,³ **Pedro Coelho**,^{4,5,6} **Joana Gomes**,^{4,5}
Celso A. Reis,^{4,5,6,7} **Pedro M. P. Góis**³ and **Filipa Marcelo**^{1,2}

¹Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; ²UCIBIO, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal; ³Research Institute for Medicines (iMed.U LISBOA), Faculdade de Farmácia, Universidade de Lisboa, 1600-277 Lisboa, Portugal; ⁴i3S - Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde, Universidade do Porto, 4200-135 Porto, Portugal; ⁵IPATIMUP - Institute of Molecular Pathology and Immunology, University of Porto, 4200-135 Porto, Portugal; ⁶ICBAS - Instituto de Ciências Biomédicas Abel Salazar, Universidade do Porto, 4050-313 Porto, Portugal; ⁷Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, University of Porto, 4200-319 Porto, Portugal

cd.lima@campus.fct.unl.pt; filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

The development of new cancer therapies has been a priority for quite a long time, due to this disease being one of the major causes of death. Most of the current therapies are not effective enough and have severe secondary effects¹.

Cancer cells commonly alter mucin glycosylation, where tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens (TACAs) such as, the Tn-antigen (GalNAc α -Ser/Thr) and its sTn-antigen (Neu5Ac α 2-6GalNAc α -Ser/Thr), absent in healthy cells, are overexpressed².

The Human Macrophage Galactose-type Lectin (MGL), expressed in human macrophages and dendritic cells, has high specificity towards N-acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) containing ligands^{3,4,5}, like these TACAs. The ability to discriminate cancer cells makes MGL an attractive target for lectin-drug conjugate approaches.

Antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs) are effective therapies but lack the specificity towards cancer cells since antibodies target receptors usually expressed in normal cells, therefore MGL-drug conjugates can become an alternative strategy to develop a specific cancer-targeting drug delivery application, safer for the patients than ADCs.

In this communication, we describe our research progress in designing MGL-drug conjugates. The anti-mitotic MMAE used for ADCs, FDA approved⁶, equipped with a cleavable linker were selected. An MGL construct containing a cysteine in C-terminus was prepared for conjugation with the selected drug, following protocols already established⁷, and the reactions were followed by mass spectrometry and the protein function evaluated by NMR spectroscopy. Preliminary studies using glycoengineered cancer cell models to evaluate the binding selectivity of MGL were performed.

References

1. B. Jönsson, T. Hofmarcher, et al. Eur J Cancer. 2016, 66, 162-170.
2. S. S. Pinho, C. A. Reis. Nat Rev Cancer. 2015, 15(9), 540-555.
3. F. Marcelo, N. Supekar, et al. J Biol Chem. 2019, 294(4), 1300-1311.
4. A. Diniz, H. Coelho, et al. Chem Eur J. 2019, 25(61), 13945-13955.
5. C. D. L. Lima, H. Coelho, et al. Chem Eur J. 2021, 27(29), 7951-7958.
6. E. C. Breij, B. E. de Goeij, et al. Cancer Res. 2014, 74(4), 1214-1226.
7. Y. Wang, F. Xie, et al. Drug Deliv. 2022, 29(1), 754-766.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) for the funding projects: MGL4Life PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020, UCIBIO project UIDP/04378/2020 & UIDB/04378/2020 and, i4HB project LA/P/0140/2020. F.M. thanks FCT-Portugal for the CEEC contract CEECINST/00042/2021. C. D. L. acknowledges the PhD grant 2021.06789.BD.

Sialyl-Tn in Colorectal Cancer

Daniela A Pinto^{1,2}, Rita Adubeiro Lourenço^{1,2}, Raquel Cruz Duarte⁴, Ana Sofia Rodrigues^{1,2}, Paula Borralho⁴, Marta Martins⁴, Nuno P Ramos², Ana Rita Gross^{1,2}, Paula A Videira^{1,2,3}

¹ *i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Largo da Torre, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

² *Departamento Ciências da Vida, UCIBIO, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

³ *CDG & Allies – Professionals and Patient Associations International Network (CDG & Allies – PPAIN), 2829-516, Caparica, Portugal.*

⁴ *Instituto de Medicina Molecular-João Lobo Antunes, Faculdade de Medicina, Universidade de Lisboa, 1649-028 Lisbon, Portugal.*

dar.pinto@campus.fct.unl.pt

Sialyl-Tn (STn) antigen is a truncated sialylated O-glycan, absent from healthy tissue but expressed in over 80% of carcinomas, associated with a worse prognosis. One mechanism leading to STn overexpression in cancer is the overexpression of the sialyltransferase ST6GalNAc-I, associated with oncogenic signalling pathways. Although STn is reported in colorectal cancer (CRC), its biological and clinical impact of its expression is still unclear. Based on genetic, phenotypic and microenvironmental features, CRC can be classified into four Consensus Molecular Subtypes (CMS1, CMS2, CMS3 and CMS4), which inform prognosis and predict therapy response but still require identification of targetable candidates.

To understand the role of STn in CRC, we analysed a cohort of 208 CRC patients from whom genetic expression was determined and, also, STn levels but for only 81 patients, and found a significant positive association between STn levels and microsatellite instability (MSI). Furthermore, we observed a significant increase in ST6GALNAC1 expression in CMS3 subtype tumours compared to other subtypes. This result was further validated in a cohort from The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA), and in another cohort with single cell data available through Genome Expression Omnibus (GEO), from National Center for Biotechnology (NCBI) data repository, demonstrating a strong correlation between the expression of the gene coding for the ST6GalNAc-I enzyme and CMS3 classified tumour cells. The association of STn with MSI and increased ST6GALNAC1 expression in the CMS3 subtype can have significant implications regarding targeted therapy and patient stratification.

Mucin glycoprotein microarray for glycan ligand discovery of bacterial modular proteins

**Filipa Trovão^{1,2}, Jodie Abrahams³, Antonio Di Maio³, Jin Yu³, Wengang Chai³,
Ten Feizi³, Ana Luísa Carvalho^{1,2}, Yan Liu³, Angelina S. Palma^{1,2}**

¹UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

²Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2819-516 Caparica, Portugal;

³Glycosciences Laboratory, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction, Imperial College London, W12 0NN, London, United Kingdom.

f.trovao@campus.fct.unl.pt

The intestinal epithelium mucus layer contains extensively O-glycosylated proteins – mucins. How mucin O-glycans are differentially exploited by the microbiota and influence the crosstalk with the human host largely remains to be elucidated at the molecular level¹.

The commensal gut microbiota *Bacteroides caccae* is implicated in the digestion of the colonic mucus layer in low-fibre diet conditions². During growth on mucin-type glycans, *B. caccae* showed an increased expression of modular enzymes, comprising appended non-catalytic carbohydrate-binding modules (CBMs). The hypothesis is that these CBMs facilitate mucin foraging by the bacteria and thereby render the intestinal epithelium susceptible to pathogen infection, promoting states of dysbiosis^{1,2}. To identify glycan ligands targeted by the bacterial CBMs, we developed microarrays containing mucin-enriched glycoprotein samples from diverse human epithelial cell types found in teratomatous tissues of ovarian cystadenomas. They present structurally diverse and complex O-glycans representative of the human O-glycome³.

Initial microarray screening analyses showed differential binding to various mucin-enriched cystadenoma and meconium samples suggesting the recognition of novel O-glycan ligands. Thus, these mucin glycoproteins are an important starting point for the development of mucin O-glycome beam search microarrays⁴ for discoveries of biologically relevant glycan ligands.

References

1. E. C. Martens et al., Nat. Rev. Microbiol. 2018, 16, 457-470.
2. M. S. Desai et al., Cell 2016, 167, 1339-1353.
3. T. Feizi & E. A. Kabat, J. Exp. Med. 1972, 136, 1247-1258.
4. Z. Li et al., Mol. Cell. Proteomics 2018, 17, 121-133.

Acknowledgements

This work has been carried out with financial support of national funds from the Portuguese Science and Technology Foundation (FCT-MCTES) through the project grant 2022.06104.PTDC, the fellowship SFRH/BD/143494/2019, the project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 of the Research Unit on Applied Molecular Biosciences - UCIBIO and the project LA/P/0140/2020 of the Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB. Wellcome Trust biomedical resource grants (099197/Z/12/Z, 108430/Z/15/Z, and 218304/Z/19/Z). HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning.

It takes two to tango, the importance of microbial glycans in infectious diseases development.

François Le Mauff

Glyco-NET Integrated Services, microbial glycomic node, Montreal, H4A 3J1 Québec, Canada

francois.lemauff@mail.mcgill.ca

The importance of mammalian glycans in infectious disease progression has long been established. Although some microbial glycans are well known for their immunomodulatory effects, such as the bacterial LPS or the fungal chitin, microbial glycomics remains largely underexplored. To the image of the microbial kingdom, the microbial glycomes are wide, diverse and unique. Furthermore, microbes have demonstrated incredibly creative ways to use these polysaccharides to their full potential making them integral for pathogenesis. Understanding the microbial polysaccharide structure and metabolism could therefore represent an important source of novel biomarkers and therapeutic targets.

Two examples of the microbial ingenuity and use of polysaccharide in virulence, or as treatment, can be illustrated through the results of two of our recent studies. First, the study of NleA, a protein virulence factor used by the enterohaemorrhagic and enteropathogenic *Escherichia coli* resulted in the first demonstration that a bacterial protein can acquire a mammalian glycan¹. While the specific role of this glycan remains under study, the first analysis shows that mammalian glycosylation of the bacterial protein could constitute a host defence mechanism¹. On another hand, the study of the biofilm formation by the fungal pulmonary pathogen *Aspergillus fumigatus* has demonstrated that an exogenous application of the Carbohydrate-Active Enzymes that the fungus normally uses to build its biofilm results in their degradation. More importantly, when used *in-vivo* as therapeutic agents, significant improvement in mice survival was observed^{2,3}.

As illustrated, microbial glycomics can contribute to the development of novel therapeutic responding to the urgent need for new antimicrobials.

References

1. Burns L, Le Mauff F, Gruenheid S. Direct evidence of host-mediated glycosylation of NleA and its dependence on interaction with the COPII complex. *Gut Microbes*. 2024;16(1):2305477.
2. Le Mauff F, Bamford N, Alnabelseya N, et al. Molecular mechanism of *Aspergillus fumigatus* biofilm disruption by fungal and bacterial glycoside hydrolases. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2019;jbc.RA119.008511.
3. Ostapska H, Raju D, Lehoux M, et al. Preclinical Evaluation of Recombinant Microbial Glycoside Hydrolases in the Prevention of Experimental Invasive Aspergillosis. *mBio*. 2021:e0244621.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from the Canada Foundation for Innovation program of Major Science Initiative (GlycoNET Integrated Services, grant #42481) and the Canadian Institute for Health and Research (FDN_159902) and McGill Interdisciplinary Initiative in Immunity and Infection.

Harnessing large-scale and single-cell RNA-Seq to Unveil the Landscape of Myeloid Lectins in Immunosuppressive Breast Cancer

G. Trindade^{1,2}, **S. Batalha**^{1,2}, **I. A. Isidro**^{1,2}, **C. Brito**^{1,2*}

¹*iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, Oeiras, Portugal.*

²*Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Oeiras, Portugal.*

* anabrito@ibet.pt

Breast Cancer (BC) subtypes with poor prognosis are associated with tumor microenvironments (TMEs) rich in myeloid immune cells, known to promote pro-tumorigenic immunosuppressive (IS) TMEs. Immunotherapies targeting immune suppression, typically cytokine signalling, have been proposed. Yet they faced challenges from redundancy and compensatory mechanisms, hampering clinical success. Recent findings emphasize the role of myeloid lectins, immune-modulating carbohydrate receptors that recognize aberrant glycans on tumor cells, in sustaining IS TMEs. As such, lectins are proposed as potential targets for immunotherapies, but systematic characterization of their expression pattern remains underexplored.

In this work, we profiled the lectin landscape of the myeloid cell population of tumor tissue from BC patients, to identify potential targets to block myeloid-mediated immunosuppression.

We analyzed a bulk RNA-Seq dataset (3207 patients)¹ and classified samples as IS (44%) and Non IS, using a regression model based on a classifying gene panel². HER2+ and Triple Negative tumors were overrepresented in the IS group, with decreased overall survival. Differential expression analysis of a curated list of lectin genes (116, coding immune transmembrane C- & I-Type), identified 12 upregulated in the IS group. We explored single-cell RNA-Seq datasets to define the myeloid cell subsets with expression of the identified lectins. Validation at the protein level in patient samples is ongoing and the next steps include functional validation.

In sum, we deliver a comprehensive characterization of the lectin landscape of myeloid cells within IS TME in BC, which may contain potential targets to tackle IS, rendering tumors sensitive to other immunotherapies.

References

1. H. Dalal. et al., Sci Rep. 2022, 12, 4696.
2. X. Tekpli., et al., Nat Commun. 2019, 10, 5499.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by FCT/MECI (PT) through national funds to iNOVA4Health (UIDB/04462/2020 & UIDP/04462/2020); the Associate Laboratory LS4Future (LA/P/0087/2020); the GlycoTAM project (PTDC/BTM-TEC/0432/2021); and the individual fellowship grant to G.T. (2022/11642/BD).

Strategic Deciphering of Salmonella SiiE Adhesin Specificity for Advanced Anti-Adhesion Therapy

Alicia Candeias^{1,2}, Benedita Pinheiro^{1,2}, Filipa Trovão^{1,2}, Antonio Di Maio³,
Wengang Chai³, Ten Feizi³, Yan Liu³, Aldino Viegas^{1,2}, Angelina Sá Palma^{1,2},
Filipa Marcelo^{1,2}, Helena Coelho^{1,2*}

¹Associate Laboratory i4HB – Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of
Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, Caparica 2829-516, Portugal

²UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Depart. of Chemistry, NOVA School of
Science and Technology, NOVA University of Lisbon, Caparica 2829-516, Portugal

³Glycosciences Laboratory, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction,
Imperial College London, W12 0NN, London, United Kingdom.

h.coelho@fct.unl.pt

Salmonellosis is a major foodborne health concern, with 1.35 million cases reported annually in the U.S., resulting in 26,500 hospitalizations and 420 deaths¹. The rise of antibiotic-resistant strains and the economic burden of disease management highlight the urgent need for new therapeutic strategies targeting *Salmonella*.

Salmonella adheres to host cells through specific interactions between bacterial adhesins and host cell receptors, often involving glycoproteins and glycans¹.

The non-fibrillar *Salmonella* SiiE giant adhesin targets Mucin-1 (MUC1) via sialic acid- containing O-glycans, playing a pivotal role in infection². Understanding SiiE's specificity and molecular interactions with mucin O-glycans is crucial for targeting the SiiE-MUC1 interaction, offering an alternative approach to combat bacterial resistance. Our methodology integrates glycan microarrays, mucin cell-based arrays, and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) for high-throughput screening and detailed insights into molecular structure and dynamics. This approach is essential for understanding SiiE's molecular specificity, facilitating the development of novel anti-adhesion molecules to combat *Salmonella* infections.

References

1. T. Rehman et al., *Microb. Pathog.* **2019**, 137, 103748.
2. Li, X. et al. *PLoS Pathog.* **2019**, 15, e1007566

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from the 2023.00074.RESTART project. The authors also thanks to EXPL/QUI-OUT/0069/2021, 2022.06104.PTDC, GLYCOTwinning project HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417, UIDP/04378/2020 & UIDB/04378/2020, LA/P/0140/2020, ROTEIRO/0031/2013-PINFRA/22161/2016, and R-NMR project (grant agreement n.º 101058595). H.C, AV and FM thanks also to FCT-Portugal to the CEEC contracts 10.54499/2020.03261.CEECIND/CP1586/CT0012, 2020.00043.CEECIND/CP1586/CT0022 and CEECINST/00042/2021 respectively.

Glycosyltransferase 8 domain-containing protein 1 (GLT8D1) is a UDP-dependent galactosyltransferase

**Vicente JB¹, Guerreiro ACL^{1,2}, Felgueiras B¹, Chapla D^{3,4}, Tehrani D^{3,4}, Moremen
KW^{3,4}, Costa J¹**

¹ *Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, 2780-157 Oeiras, Portugal.* ² *iBET, Instituto de Biologia Experimental e Tecnológica, Apartado 12, 2781-901 Oeiras, Portugal.*

³ *Complex Carbohydrate Research Center, University of Georgia, Athens, GA 30602, USA.* ⁴ *Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, University of Georgia, Athens, GA 30602, USA.*

jcosta@itqb.unl.pt

Glycosyltransferases (GTs) are enzymes that catalyze the formation of glycosidic bonds and hundreds of GTs have been identified so far in humans. Glycosyltransferase 8 domain-containing protein 1 (GLT8D1) belongs to the GT8 family of the CAZy database. Mutated forms of GLT8D1 were found in amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and soft tissue tumors; moreover, a genetic association of GLT8D1 with psychiatric disorders has been reported. Here, we have produced and purified recombinant secretory GLT8D1, which is an N-glycosylated protein, and have explored its substrate specificity. Differential scanning fluorimetry was employed to analyze the stabilization of GLT8D1 by Mn²⁺ and nucleotides, revealing UDP as the most stabilizing nucleotide scaffold. GLT8D1 displayed glycosyltransferase activity from UDP-galactose onto N-acetylgalactosamine¹. Modeling of the structure revealed similarities with other GT-A fold enzymes in CAZy family GT8 and glycosyltransferases in other families with galactosyl-, glucosyl-, and xylosyltransferase activities, each with retaining catalytic mechanisms. Our study provides novel insights into the properties of GLT8D1 with potential implications in pathological processes.

References

1. Vicente JB, Guerreiro ACL, Felgueiras B, Chapla D, Tehrani D, Moremen KW, Costa J, *Sci Rep* **2023**, 13, 21684.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I. P. through iNOVA4Health (UIDB/04462/2020, UIDP/04462/2020) and LS4FUTURE Associated Laboratory (LA/P/0087/2020) (to J.C. and J.B.V.) and by US NIH Grants GM130915, GM103390, and GM107012 (to K.W.M.).

From Ratio to Reality: Compositional Analysis of Comparative Glycomics with Glycowork

**J. Lundström^{1,2}, A.R. Bennet³, J. Urban^{1,2}, S. Chatterjee⁴, M. Thaysen-Andersen^{4,5},
D. Bojar^{1,2}**

¹Department of Chemistry and Molecular Biology, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden; ²Wallenberg Centre for Molecular and Translational Medicine, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden; ³Department of Medical Biochemistry, Institute of Biomedicine, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, Sweden; ⁴School of Natural Sciences, Faculty of Science and Engineering, Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia; ⁵Institute for Glyco-core Research (iGCORE), Nagoya University, Nagoya, Japan
jon.lundstrom@gu.se, daniel.bojar@gu.se

In the era of ‘omics, the comprehensive analysis of glycan structures has emerged as an important field with substantial relevance for understanding biology and disease mechanisms. However, both glycan structural complexity and the compositional nature of glycomics data significantly complicate efforts to analyze differential abundance between conditions. Addressing these challenges, we have developed a methodological toolbox comprising specialized and domain-informed approaches for data normalization and imputation, glycan motif extraction and quantification, differential expression analysis, motif enrichment analysis, time series analysis, and meta-analytic capabilities¹. In recent work, we further extend this framework with the introduction of normalization approaches specifically tailored for compositional data, as well as new analysis modalities to explore cross-class glycan correlations and glycan distributions within and between samples². Taken together, our rigorous approach allows for more robust, reliable, and comprehensive differential expression analyses in glycomics, contributing to the advancement of glycomics research and its translation to clinical and diagnostic applications.

References

1. J. Lundström, J. Urban, D. Bojar, Cell Rep Methods, **2023**.
2. A.R. Bennett, J. Lundström, S. Chatterjee, M. Thaysen-Andersen, D. Bojar, bioRxiv. **2024**.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by a Branco Weiss Fellowship – Society in Science awarded to D.B.; by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation; and the University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

GlyCoDA: A compositional data analysis and domain adaptation perspective on disease risk prediction using plasma IgG N-glycans

Konstantinos Flevaris, Irena Trbojević-Akmačić, Gordan Lauc, Cleo Kontoravdi

Exhibition Rd, South Kensington, London, SW72AZ

k.flevaris21@imperial.ac.uk

Disease-specific biomarkers are crucial for managing chronic diseases through early diagnosis and screening. Plasma IgG N-glycans show promise as minimally invasive, modifiable biomarkers due to their plasticity in response to genetic and environmental factors¹. However, the analysis of glycomic datasets for biomarker discovery presents unique challenges: these datasets often comprise small to moderate sample sizes from demographically diverse cohorts² and represent compositional data (CoDA), where each glycan is characterized by its relative abundance as part of a whole³. To unlock the full biomarker potential of IgG glycomics, bespoke data analysis and machine learning (ML) techniques are required to develop reliable predictive tools for disease screening. This study proposes an ML-based N-glycomic analysis framework to develop classification models that capture disease-specific glycosylation variations while minimizing the influence of cohort-specific covariates. By coupling learnable log-contrast models⁴ with domain adaptation (DA) techniques, our framework aims to achieve robust generalization across cohorts with different characteristics. The proposed framework was designed and tested using inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) glycomic datasets from four cohorts. This open-source computational framework seeks to support the translation of glycan-based biomarkers into clinical applications.

References

1. S. Shkunnikova, A. Mijakovac, L. Sironic, M. Hanic, G. Lauc, M. M. Kavur, *Biotechnol. Adv.* **2023**, 67, 108169
2. I. Trbojević-Akmačić, G. S. M. Lageveen-Kammeijer, B. Heijs, T. Petrović, H. Deriš, M. Wuhler, G. Lauc, *Chem. Rev.* 2022, 122, 15865.
3. A. R. Bennett, J. Lundstrøm, S. Chatterjee, M. Thaysen-Andersen, D. Bojar, *bioRxiv* **2024**, 2024.06.09.598163.
4. T. Quinn, D. Nguyen, S. Rana, S. Gupta, S. Venkatesh, *PLMR* **2020**.

Acknowledgments

KF thanks the Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial, for their scholarship.

Targeting Human Macrophage Galactose-Type Lectin with Multivalent Glycomimetics

Alejandra Travecedo,^{1,2} **Ana Gimeno**,^{3,4} **Jesús Jimenez-Barbero**,^{3,4} **Fayna Garcia-Martin**,⁵ **Filipa Marcelo**^{1,2}

¹UCIBIO, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829- 516 Caparica, Portuga ²Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal ³CIC bioGUNE, Basque Research and Technology Alliance, Bizkaia Technology Park, Ed. 800. E-48160, Derio, Spain ⁴Ikerbasque, Basque Foundation for Science, Euskadi Plaza 5, 48009 Bilbao, Bizkaia, Spain ⁵Departamento de Química, Universidad de La Rioja, Centro de Investigación en Síntesis Química, 26006 Logroño, Spain
m.travecedo@campus.fct.unl.pt filipa.marcelo@fct.unl.pt

Macrophage galactose-type lectin (MGL), located in dendritic cells and macrophages, plays a crucial role in various immune responses through the recognition of N- acetylgalactosamine (GalNAc) sugars. One significant example of these immune responses is the mediation of Ebola virus entry by interacting with GalNAc-containing glycoproteins. The rational design of molecules to block these viral interactions is an attractive strategy for the development of novel immunotherapies. To inhibit Ebola virus entry by targeting MGL, multivalent glycomimetics were developed. Given that monovalent glycan-protein interactions are typically weak, nature compensates with multivalent interactions, making it essential to take in account multivalency when designing inhibitors. In this study, we report on the molecular recognition of dimeric, tetrameric, and octameric glycomimetics containing GalNAc motifs by MGL, utilizing ¹H,¹⁵N-HSQC-based titrations and ITC measurements.

References

1. SJ van Vliet, E van Liempt et al. *Int Immunol.* 2005;17(5):661–9.
2. (a) A. Takada, et al. *J. Virol.*, 2004, 78, 2943; (b) S. Van Vliet, et al. *Trends in Immun.*, 2008, 29, 83.
3. M Martínez-Bailén, J Rojo, Ramos-Soriano *J. Chem Soc Rev.* **2022**;52(2):536–72.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT-Portugal) for the funding projects: MGL4Life DOI 10.54499/PTDC/QUI-OUT/2586/2020, UCIBIO project UIDP/04378/2020 and UIDB/04378/2020 and Associate Laboratory Institute for Health and Bioeconomy - i4HB project LA/P/0140/2020). F.M. thank FCT-Portugal for the CEEC Institutional contract CEECINST/00042/2021. The NMR spectrometers are part of the National NMR Facility supported by FCT-Portugal (ROTEIRO/0031/2013- PINFRA/22161/2016, cofinanced by FEDER through COMPETE 2020, POCI and PORL and FCT through PIDDAC). F.M. and J.J.B acknowledge EU funding for the GLYCOTwinning project.

Advancing Understanding of Gut Microbiota-Glycosylation Interactions in Gastrointestinal Diseases: A Data-Driven Approach

Rocio Gonzalez-Soltero^{1,2}, Ana Rita Grosso^{3,4}, Paula A. Videira^{3,4}

¹*Faculty of Biomedicine and Health. Universidad Europea de Madrid. Spain*

²*Molecular Microbiology Research Group. Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria del H. Universitario La Paz – IdiPAZ, (Madrid, Spain)*

³*UCIBIO – Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal*

⁴*Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal*

mariadelrocio.gonzalez@universidadeuropea.es

Understanding the interactions between the gut microbiota and glycome is crucial for advancing knowledge in glycosylation – related diseases and gastrointestinal (GI) diseases. Studies have shown that the gut microbiota can induce specific epithelial glycosylation patterns, such as α 1,2 fucose expression. The FUT2 gene encodes an enzyme responsible for the α 1,2 fucosylation of epithelial cells. Variations in FUT2 expression, influenced by the gut microbiota, have significant clinical implications for GI diseases such as IBD. Individuals with non-functional FUT2 alleles (non-secretors) have altered gut microbiota composition and are at higher risk for IBD.

The study presented here aims to explore how specific gut microorganisms influence epithelial glycosylation patterns by analysing gene expression of glycogenes through data reuse. This analysis could offer insights into personalized therapeutic strategies and enhance our understanding of gut health and disease susceptibility. The main objective of the study is to establish a comprehensive data research strategy based on data reuse for locating relevant datasets and studies with a focus on gut microbiota, and glycome related genetic factors using bibliographic and databases (e.g., GlyGen, TCGA). As secondary objectives we propose to use generative artificial intelligence tools to look for interactions between gut microbiota and glycome with the following points: (1) the induction of epithelial glycosylation by gut microbiota, and (2) the clinical relevance of glycosyltransferase expression in GI diseases.

A comprehensive bibliographic search using terms related to microbiome and glycome and glycogenes is under analysis. We prepared a microbiome and gene expression matching dataset from a small cohort of samples obtained from young individuals. The glycogenes will be identified using methodologies previously described².

The following steps are underway:

- Standardizing data formats. Standardized ontologies and data formats will be used to ensure interoperability and compatibility across different data sets³.
- Data Extraction and Synthesis: Generative AI tools will be used for data extraction and synthesis to identify patterns, and relationships across studies⁴.

- **Quality Assessment:** to assess the quality and risk of bias in included studies using appropriate tools (e.g., Cochrane Risk of Bias tool, AMSTAR).

This research explores how specific gut microorganisms influence glycosylation patterns and may underscore the clinical relevance of glycogenes, providing insights into personalized therapeutic strategies and enhancing our understanding of gut health and disease susceptibility.

References

1. Kudelka MR, Stowell SR, Cummings RD, Neish AS. Intestinal epithelial glycosylation in homeostasis and gut microbiota interactions in IBD. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol.* **2020**; 17(10):597-617. doi: 10.1038/s41575-020-0331-7
2. Sobral D, Francisco R, Duro L, Videira PA, Grosso AR. Concerted Regulation of Glycosylation Factors Sustains Tissue Identity and Function. *Biomedicines.* **2022** Jul 27;10(8):1805. doi: 10.3390/biomedicines10081805.
3. Von Der Lieth, C. W., Bohne-Lang, A., Lohmann, K. K., & Frank, M. Bioinformatics for glycomics: status, methods, requirements and perspectives. *Briefings in bioinformatics,* **2004.** 5(2), 164-178.
4. Kurilshikov, A., Medina-Gomez, C., Bacigalupe, R., Radjabzadeh, D., Wang, J., Demirkan, A., ... & Zhernakova, A. Large-scale association analyses identify host factors influencing human gut microbiome composition. *Nature genetics,* **2021.** 53(2), 156-165.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried with the financial support of Santander Universidades granted to Rocio Gonzalez Soltero for a short stay at NOVA University of Lisboa.

Optimization of Cell Surface N-Glycoproteomics Analysis to Map the Colorectal Cancer Glycome

Nika Šimičić, Juan C. Rojas Echeverri, Dario A. T. Cramer, Arnoud de Ru, Jordy van Angeren, Isa van Heusden, Manfred Wuhrer, Noortje de Haan

Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics, Leiden University Medical Center, Albinusdreef 2, 2333 ZA Leiden, The Netherlands

n.simicic@lumc.nl

Colorectal cancer (CRC) incidences are increasing at a young age (before 50), and early-stage detection of CRC is essential for successful treatment, emphasizing a high demand for discovering new molecular targets.¹ Aberrant glycosylation of cell surface proteins has been associated with all hallmarks of cancer, highlighting their high potential as new CRC molecular targets.² However, covering a wide range of cancer-associated cell surface glycoproteins in one experiment is still challenging. Here, we aim to optimize the sample preparation and data analysis of glycoproteomic samples, ultimately allowing us to investigate the cell surface N-glycosylation of CRC cells.

To this end, human plasma was used as a model sample, achieving the analysis of 8 and 80 µg plasma protein without losing N-glycoproteome information. The optimized approach was combined with cell surface-specific protein labeling and applied to the intestinal human colon adenocarcinoma cell line LS180, identifying around 1,000 glycopeptides from 100 cellular glycoproteins, including cancer-associated glycoproteins.³ CRC-associated glycoforms were identified for functionally relevant cell surface proteins, epidermal growth factor receptor, and integrin beta 1. Applying this method to phenotypically different CRC cell lines has the potential to identify CRC-associated glycopeptides and corresponding glycoproteins as biomarkers.

References

1. Biller, L. H.; Schrag, D., *JAMA* **2021**, 325 (7), 669-685.
2. Čaval, T.; Alisson-Silva, F.; Schwarz, F., *Theranostics* **2023**, 13 (8), 2605-2615.
3. de Haan, N.; Song, M.; Grant, O. C.; Ye, Z.; Khoder Agha, F.; Koed Møller Aasted, M.; Woods, R. J.; Vakhrushev, S. Y.; Wandall, H. H. *Analytical Chemistry* **2023**, 95 (47), 17328-17336.

Acknowledgments

*This research was financially supported by **Health~Holland (TARGlycan)** and **EU HORIZON (GLYCOTwinning and GlycanTrigger)**.*

Streamlining oligosaccharide and glycan synthesis with mutant glycoside hydrolases.

Rajneesh Bains^{1,2}, Feng Liu^{1,2}, Seyed Nasser^{1,2}, Jacob Wardman^{2,3}, Stephen G. Withers^{1,2,3}

¹ Department of Chemistry, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada

² Michael Smith Laboratories, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada

³ Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, University of British Columbia, Vancouver, BC, Canada
rheabains@chem.ubc.ca

N- and O-Glycans play important roles in health and disease. Despite their significance, our understanding of the functional roles associated with specific glycoforms remains limited. The inherent heterogeneity of protein glycosylation poses a significant challenge in establishing clear structure function relationships for specific glycans. Given that most therapeutic proteins are glycosylated, there is great interest in generating glycoproteins with defined glycans to investigate the effects bestowed by distinct glycoforms. This, in turn, may help enable the identification of “optimal” glycosylation patterns for more effective biotherapeutics. However, to facilitate a structure-function understanding of various glycoforms, and their relevant binding proteins we must expand the existing toolkit to prepare defined oligosaccharides and glycans. Enzymatic approaches with high regio- and stereoselective control are preferred over more complex synthetic routes. Thus, there remains a demand for cost-effective enzymatic tools to streamline the preparation of biologically relevant oligosaccharides and glycans. Utilizing mutant glycoside hydrolases (GHs) in conjunction with activated donors emerges as a compelling strategy for the synthesis of target oligosaccharides. Our ongoing efforts focus on employing mutant GHs with inexpensive activated donors to prepare a variety of oligosaccharides and glycans, including sulfated glycans, which are implicated in health and disease. Our approach constitutes a cost-effective in vitro strategy for the preparation of well-defined glycoforms and oligosaccharides, that are otherwise challenging to obtain. Such substrates can be used for various applications, such as in glycan arrays, glycan remodeling efforts, and probing their interactions with carbohydrate binding proteins such as lectins.

Direct imaging of single RNAs

Shengpeng Huang¹, Klaus Kern^{1,2}, and Kelvin Anggara¹

¹*Max Planck Institute for Solid State Research*

²*Institute de Physique, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne*

s.huang@fkf.mpg.de

Ribonucleic acid (RNA) plays key roles in many biological processes, including gene expression, protein synthesis, chemical catalysis, and cellular regulation. Despite its ubiquity, understanding flexible RNA structures remain challenging with ensemble-averaged methods, such as X-ray crystallography, cryo electron microscopy, and nuclear magnetic resonance.

We confront this problem by direct imaging of RNAs deposited on surfaces, which offers an interesting possibility to determine directly the RNA sequence and its consequent three-dimensional structures. We employ the Electrospray Ion Beam Deposition (ESIBD) technique to transfer intact RNA molecules in a solution onto a surface in vacuo, which are subsequently imaged by Scanning Tunnelling Microscopy (STM). Using our ESIBD+STM approach, we have successfully deposited and imaged single chains of intact 60-mer RNA, which allows individual RNA chains to be structurally characterized at the single nucleotide level. Single molecule imaging of RNA presents a new approach to structurally determine many interesting post-translational modifications (PTMs) of RNAs with important biological roles.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from ERC Starting Grant GlycoX.

Investigating Glycan Binding and Mutation Effects on SARS-CoV-2 N-Terminal Domain of spike protein on Viral Entry and Cell-Cell Fusion

P. Lapphaisal¹, S. Visamol², A. Thititanyanont², A. Imberty³, S. Kuhaudomlarp¹

¹*Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, Mahidol University, Bangkok, 10400 Thailand*

²*Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Science, Mahidol University, Bangkok 10400, Thailand*

³*CERMAV, University Grenoble Alpes, CNRS, 38000 Grenoble, France*

Sakonwan.kuh@mahidol.edu

The role of viral lectins in the attachment of SARS-CoV-2 to host glycans remains a significant yet understudied area. While the receptor-binding domain (RBD) of the spike protein is known to bind ACE2, the function of the N-terminal domain (NTD) is less clear, with evidence suggesting its potential as a sialic acid binding site. Our work explores the lectin-like properties of NTDs from SARS-CoV-2 and SARS-related CoV RaTG13 using surface plasmon resonance (SPR) to elucidate their interactions with sialylated glycans. Our results demonstrate a strong affinity of the SARS-CoV-2 WT NTD for sialylated glycan, with a dissociation constant (K_D) of 0.54 ± 0.04 nM, highlighting its role in glycan binding. We further assessed the impact of specific NTD mutations within the sialic acid binding site on viral entry and cell-to-cell fusion. Using spike-bearing pseudotyped virus assays, we showed that the $\Delta 69$ mutation reduced viral entry into host cells, while the $\Delta 145$ mutation increased viral entry. Additionally, the $\Delta 145$ mutation resulted in a higher number of cell-cell fusions compared to the $\Delta 69$ mutation, indicating differential effects on viral infectivity and syncytia formation. Our findings underscore the complexity of NTD-mediated interactions in viral-host dynamics and suggest that targeting glycan-NTD interactions could be a potential strategy for developing antiviral inhibitors. Understanding these glycan interactions and the impact of NTD mutations may pave the way for novel therapeutic approaches to mitigate SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Acknowledgments

This project is funded by National Research Council of Thailand (NRCT) grant no. N41A640121 and Development and Promotion of Science and Technology Talents Project (DPST). Royal Government of Thailand scholarship. The project is also supported by FRANCO-THAI MOBILITY PROGRAMME (PHC SIAM) 2021-2022.

Unveiling GlycoBiases: Biosynthetic network-driven insights into physiological glycan preferences of glycosyltransferases

Ujala Bashir, Daniel Bojar

Department of Chemistry and Molecular Biology, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, 41390 Sweden

Wallenberg Centre for Molecular and Translational Medicine, University of Gothenburg, Gothenburg, 41390 Sweden

daniel.bojar@gu.se

Glycosyltransferases (GTs) are pivotal enzymes that facilitate the biosynthesis of all glycans, which are ubiquitously present as various glycoconjugates across all organisms. It is known that GTs exhibit preferences for aspects such as glycan class or sequence context. However, most of these GT preferences have been catalogued *in vitro*, with single, purified, enzymes, with unclear ramifications for their preferences in the enzymatic cascade within a cellular context. Additionally, the evolutionary conservation of such preferences, and the consequences on glycomes across diverse organisms, represent a promising yet underinvestigated research area.

The biosynthetic network pipeline of the Python package glycowork¹, which leverages evolutionary relationships and inferred intermediates, provides a robust framework for exploring glycan biosynthesis and its evolutionary impact². By employing network analysis, we elucidate the information embedded within the biosynthetic network across a wide range of glycomics datasets to: (i) identify reaction pathway preferences and sequences, (ii) estimate reaction rates for specific enzymatic processes, (iii) explain reaction order based on glycan features that may inhibit enzyme activity, (iv) analyze the conservation of these patterns across various glycan classes and species to enhance our understanding of evolutionary systematic biases in glycomes, and (v) identify changes in biosynthetic patterns between healthy glycomes and those from diseased samples. These newfound insights are expected to significantly advance our understanding of glycan biosynthesis, its evolutionary relevance, and its regulation in health and disease.

References

1. J. Lundstrøm, L. Thomès, D. Bojar, STAR Protoc. 2024, 5, 102937
2. L. Thomès, V. Karlsson, J. Lundstrøm, D. Bojar, Cell Rep. 2023, 7, 112710.

Acknowledgments

This work is funded by a Branco Weiss Fellowship – Society in Science awarded to Daniel Bojar, by the Knut and Alice Wallenberg Foundation, and by the University of Gothenburg, Sweden.

Novel insights into mucin O-glycans recognition by commensal bacteria from the human gut microbiome

Viviana G. Correia^{1,2}, Raquel L. Costa^{1,2}, Filipa Trovão^{1,2}, Sandra Behren³, Antonio Di Maio⁴, Ulrika Westerlind³, Tem Feizi⁴, Wengang Chai⁴, Yan Liu⁴, Benedita A. Pinheiro^{1,2}, Ana Luísa Carvalho^{1,2} and Angelina S. Palma^{1,2,4}

1. UCIBIO, Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Chemistry/Department of Life Sciences, School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal; 2. Associate Laboratory i4HB, Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, School of Science and Technology, NOVA University Lisbon, Portugal; 3. Umeå University, Department of Chemistry, Sweden; 4. Glycosciences Laboratory, Department of Metabolism, Digestion and Reproduction, Imperial College London, United Kingdom

vivianacorreia@campus.fct.unl.pt

The human gut microbiome plays a vital role in targeting and utilizing glycans from our diet and mucin glycans from the mucosal intestinal layer, impacting host nutrition, immunity, and infection susceptibility^{1,2}. The exploitation of mucin O-glycans by intestinal bacteria and their influence on host crosstalk remain largely unexplored at the molecular level.

Abundant colonic bacteria, like *Bacteroides* species, possess polysaccharide utilization loci (PULs) that enable adaptation to glycan substrate variations^{1,2}. Each PUL encodes proteins for recognizing and breaking down specific glycans, including carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes) with carbohydrate-binding modules (CBMs) and other glycan-binding proteins^{1,2}.

We report the functional and structural characterization of newly identified glycan-binding proteins from *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* with increased activity on mucin O-glycans under a low-fiber diet. Using an integrative strategy, we combined bioinformatic analysis, high-throughput protein production, ligand discovery via glycan microarrays³⁻⁵, and structural characterization by X-ray crystallography⁶. Our findings elucidate the molecular basis for the unique specificities of glycan-binding proteins targeting fucosylated Lewis A and mucin O-GalNAc-Thr/Ser core structures.

Uncovering the molecular determinants for mucin O-glycan recognition by bacterial systems can help understand the role of commensals in gut health and potentiate new therapeutic and diagnostic strategies.

References

1. Martens, E.C.; et al. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **2018**, *16*, 457-470.
2. Desai, M.S.; et al. *Cell* **2016**, *167*, 1339-1353.
3. Li, Z.; et al. *Mol. Cell. Proteomics* **2018**, *17*, 121-133.
4. Li, C.; et al. *Glycobiology* **2021**, *31*, 931-946.
5. Pett, C.; Westerlind, U. *Chemistry* **2014**, *20*, 7287-7299.
6. Correia, V.G.; et al. *Microbiol. Spectr.* **2021**, *9*, e01826-21.

Acknowledgments

Work supported by FCT-MCTES grants (PTDC/BBB-BEP/0869/2014, PTDC/BIA-MIB/31730/2017, 2022.06104.PTDC), fellowships & contracts (PD/BD/105727/2014, PD/BD/135517/2018, SFRH/BD/143494/2019, DL-57/2016), projects (UIDB/04378/2020, LA/P/0140/2020, RECI/BBB-BEP/0124/2012); HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-101079417-GLYCOTwinning; and by Wellcome Trust Biomedical Resource grants (099197/Z/12/Z, 108430/Z/15/Z, and 218304/Z/19/Z).

A SENSITIVE, LABEL-FREE ANALYTICAL WORKFLOW TO CHARACTERISE HEPARAN SULPHATE FROM THE EXTRACELLULAR MATRIX OF CELLS AND TISSUES

H Davies-Strickleton^{1,2,*}, George Taylor², Rebecca L. Miller³, David Knight², Douglas P. Dyer¹

¹Discovery Research Platform, Cell Matrix Biology and Regenerative Medicine, Faculty of Biology, Medicine and Health, University of Manchester, UK

²BioMS Facility, Faculty of Biology, Medicine and Health, University of Manchester, UK

³Copenhagen Center for Glycomics, Department of Cellular and Molecular Medicine, Faculty of Health Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Denmark

*h.davies-strickleton@manchester.ac.uk

The extracellular matrix is a complex network of macromolecules that surrounds and supports cells and accounts for one third of our body mass. Many matrix components are glycosylated, including glycosaminoglycans, proteoglycans, N-linked glycoproteins, O-linked glycoproteins and mucins, and they have diverse interactions with proteins and cells. Here, as part of the new Discovery Research Platform at the University of Manchester, I am establishing a range of glycomics tools to study matrix components. So far, we have developed a highly sensitive, robust method to identify, characterise and quantify heparan sulphate in tissues and cells. Our methodology builds on those established previously [1] and incorporates analysis by HILIC chromatography and a 7600 Triple TOF MS with Zeno trapping to quantify the core heparan sulphate disaccharides. With this tool, and others as we develop them, we can start to explore changes to the glycomatrix across tissues and disease states.

References

1. B Yang, Y Chang, A M Weyers, E Sterner and R J Linhardt, *J Chromatogr A*. **2012**, 1225, 91-98.

Acknowledgments

This work has been carried out with financial support from the Wellcome Trust Discovery Research Platform.